

Regulatory Quality in the Global Innovation Index

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The variable "regulatory quality" in the context of the Global Innovation Index (GII) refers to the quality of a country's regulatory environment, which directly influences an economy's ability to innovate. This indicator measures the effectiveness and predictability of the regulatory system in supporting innovative activities, including laws, regulations, and institutions that promote competitiveness, intellectual property protection, and transparency. High regulatory quality implies a stable and consistent legislative system, capable of fostering investor confidence and stimulating the development of new ideas, technologies, and innovative enterprises. In the GII assessment, regulatory quality is considered a crucial factor in establishing the operational context in which companies and organizations operate. Countries with high regulatory quality scores tend to have rules that facilitate market entry, protect commercial interests, and encourage fair competition. In contrast, countries with low regulatory quality may discourage innovation due to unstable rules, corruption, or excessive bureaucracy. Therefore, the GII uses regulatory quality as an indicator to understand how the regulatory environment can positively or negatively impact a country's innovation capacity, recognizing it as a fundamental component of the innovation ecosystem. The data refers to the period between 2013 and 2022.

Regulatory Quality in 2022. The analysis of "regulatory quality" in the Global Innovation Index 2022 shows how countries with effective and well-structured regulation are able to promote an environment conducive to innovation, essential for economic development. Singapore achieves the maximum score of 100, highlighting a particularly favorable and stable regulatory environment. With a clear and predictable regulatory framework, Singapore stands out as an example of the ability to attract foreign investment and foster entrepreneurship and technological development. Other countries like New Zealand (91.8), Finland (91.2), and Luxembourg (90.9) follow closely, maintaining high scores thanks to advanced regulatory structures that support innovation and economic competitiveness. Nordic and Western European countries, including Denmark, the Netherlands, Norway, and Sweden,

maintain scores between 86 and 89, reflecting a stable regulatory system that is generally favorable for growth and innovation. These countries, known for their transparency and bureaucratic efficiency, offer fertile ground for the development of advanced technologies and innovative start-ups, which are fundamental to their global competitiveness. Canada (84.8) and Switzerland (84.6) also stand out for regulatory quality, which confirms their position as highly innovative economies and attractive destinations for international investors. In the United States, a score of 76 indicates good regulatory quality, although lower than some European and Asian economies. This score reflects a generally stable regulatory environment but one that could benefit from improvements to reduce legislative uncertainties in some sectors, which occasionally hinder rapid technological advancement. Countries such as Israel (75.9) and Japan (78.7), while showing high-quality regulation, could further benefit from regulatory simplification to strengthen their innovation ecosystems. Other countries with moderate scores, like Spain (64.1) and Italy (57.5), show room for improvement. In these cases, sometimes complex and shifting regulations can limit the agility of the innovation system, making it harder for new businesses to establish themselves and compete globally. Low regulatory quality can become a significant barrier to entry for foreign investments and innovative companies, making the environment less competitive. At the lower end of the rankings, we find countries like India (41.5), Vietnam (41.2), and Brazil (40.9), where bureaucratic inefficiency and regulatory instability pose additional challenges to innovation. These countries could significantly strengthen their innovation ecosystems by improving regulatory policies, fostering a more open and welcoming environment for new businesses and investments. Finally, at the lowest levels are countries such as Algeria (12.7), Iran (8.5), and Yemen (0), where a weak or nonexistent regulatory system represents a strong obstacle to economic development and innovation. In summary, the Global Innovation Index 2022 data highlights the importance of regulatory quality as a key factor in promoting an innovative environment. Countries with high-quality regulation manage to create favorable conditions for innovation and technological development, while those with low scores demonstrate the need for reforms to reduce regulatory obstacles and promote sustainable economic growth.

Regulatory Quality from 2013 to 2022. The data on the improvement and deterioration of "regulatory quality" between 2013 and 2022 in the Global Innovation Index reveals significant changes in the regulatory environment of numerous countries, with some economies strengthening regulatory quality while others experienced considerable declines. Among the improvements, Uzbekistan stands out, with a score increase of 13.4 points, equivalent to a 167.5% growth. This reflects efforts toward regulatory reform and economic openness, introducing more transparent regulations and attracting foreign investment. Other countries, such as Belarus and Côte d'Ivoire, also recorded significant increases of 59.44% and 40.22%, respectively, signaling attempts to modernize the regulatory system to create a more business-friendly and innovation-oriented environment. In these cases, regulatory reforms likely brought greater clarity and predictability for economic operators, fostering the growth of entrepreneurial activities and new investments. The United Arab Emirates, despite already having a high starting score, further increased its regulatory quality by 20%, solidifying its position as one of the most open and well-regulated economies in the region. The rise in regulatory quality in countries like Vietnam and Indonesia, with respective increases of 22.62% and 14.11%, indicates a push for administrative efficiency and a reduction in bureaucracy to facilitate business activities and boost global competitiveness. On the other hand, several countries, including developed economies like the United States, Canada, and the United Kingdom, experienced declines in regulatory quality. The United States saw a decrease of 12.3 points (-13.93%), potentially linked to an increase in regulatory complexity or legislative uncertainties in key sectors such as technology and healthcare. Canada and the United Kingdom, with declines of 9.3% and 10.88%, respectively, may reflect changes in the regulatory landscape that could limit their economies' flexibility and adaptability in a competitive context. In Europe, countries like Spain, Belgium, and France also saw reductions in regulatory quality, with decreases of -17.93%, -4.37%, and -4.71%, respectively, which may suggest greater regulatory rigidity or administrative complications that hinder entrepreneurial agility. The

decline in regulatory quality in established economies suggests that, while the regulatory environment remains relatively strong, a lack of rapid adaptation to global changes may present an obstacle for companies, which find it more challenging to operate in less predictable and more complex environments. Emerging countries like Brazil and Nigeria experienced significant declines, with drops of -24.12% and -34.07%, respectively. These changes indicate systemic challenges, such as increased bureaucracy and a lack of regulatory stability, which prevent the creation of a favorable business environment and reduce attractiveness to foreign investors. Similarly, other African countries, such as Ghana and Tunisia, experienced significant declines, highlighting the need for reforms to improve regulatory transparency and stability. In summary, the data shows that improvements in regulatory quality contribute significantly to economic growth and innovation. However, reductions in regulatory quality can hinder development, particularly in emerging economies that depend on their ability to attract foreign investment and support entrepreneurial initiatives.

Conclusions. The value of regulatory quality decreased between 2013 and 2022, from 57.5 units to an average of 52.5 units among the countries considered, equating to a reduction of -8.46%. The top performers are Uzbekistan with +167.50%, Belarus with +59.44%, Iran with +51.79%, Côte d'Ivoire with +40.22%, and Togo with +27.43%. The worst performers are Honduras with -30.19%, Trinidad and Tobago with -30.83%, Egypt with -32.27%, Nigeria with -34.07%, and Algeria with -34.20%.

Performers	Country	2013	2022	Var Ass	Var Per
Top Performers	Uzbekistan	8	21,4	13,4	167,50
	Belarus	18	28,7	10,7	59,44
	Iran, Islamic Rep.	5,6	8,5	2,9	51,79
	Cote d'Ivoire	27,1	38	10,9	40,22
	Togo	23,7	30,2	6,5	27,43
	Honduras	46,7	32,6	-14,1	-30,19

Worse Performers	Trinidad and Tobago	60	41,5	-18,5	-30,83
	Egypt, Arab Rep.	40,9	27,7	-13,2	-32,27
	Nigeria	31,7	20,9	-10,8	-34,07
	Algeria	19,3	12,7	-6,6	-34,20

Fonte: *Global Innovation Index*

Link: <https://prosperitydata360.worldbank.org/en/indicator/WIPO+GII+15>

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